

A Signature Verification System for Class Attendance Records

Okorie E.,

emeka.okorie@tansianuniversity.edu.ng.

Department of computer science Tansian University Umunya Anambra State,

Nwaukwa C.J

Nwaukwaj@veritas.edu.ng.

Department of computer science Veritas University Abuja,

Chukwura S.C.

Somtychuks@gmail.com

Department of computer science Tansian University Umunya Anambra State,

Oduah O.

oduahobinna621@gmail.com.

Department of Computer Science ESUT Enugu.

Abstract -- The project presents design and implementation of an artificial intelligent based signature verification system for class attendance management. The aim was to solve the problem of impersonation and ensure that unauthorized persons do not have access to academic proceedings. The study used the agile methodology. The methods used in the system development are data collection, data processing, feature extraction, clustering and verification of outcome. In the data processing, techniques such as binarization and edge detection were used to process the signature data, before they are extracted with graphical feature extraction method for training with clustering algorithm and then verify the student. The system was implemented with Matlab programming language and the evaluated. The result showed that the software was able to verify authenticities of students during class attendance verification correctly.

Keywords -- *Data processing, artificial intelligence, signature verification*

I. BACKGROUND OF STUDY

The utilization of signature applications is experiencing rapid growth alongside technological advancements in e-banking, e-financing, e-commerce, and various other domains. It is crucial to verify collected signatures in order to establish their authenticity and prevent impersonation (Brault and Plamondon, 2017). Additionally, this verification process determines the level of integrity of the deployed systems (Ahemed, 2019). The collection of signature samples can occur either offline or online, depending on the available technology (Breebaart et al., 2018; Batista, 2012; Chakraborty et al., 2019). Offline signature collection involves acquiring signatures on hardcopy paper, whereas online signature collection entails capturing dynamic properties of the signature along with a high-quality static image. This method is typically implemented using a digital signature pad. Once the online signature samples have been gathered, it becomes essential to have a system that can virtually interface with the digital signatures and process them for acceptance or rejection. This process is known as signature verification (Ameral et al., 2019). Before signature verification can be accomplished, several significant engineering procedures must be employed, including image processing techniques and machine learning methods, among others.

II. OVERVIEW OF SIGNATURE VERIFICATION SYSTEM

For many years, signatures have served as a means of identification on paper. So, why not utilize them for biometrics? Various aspects of a signature can be examined, such as measuring the peaks, their inclination, or determining the information within a specific window. Signature systems only observe the outcome of the action—the signature itself—during user identification, making them suitable for forensic biometrics (Cummings and Cater, 2019). However, these systems are susceptible to signature imitations, which can be easily replicated in many cases (Crane and Ostrem, 2019). In contrast, online systems not only measure the signature but also take into account additional factors like pen inclination and pressure exertion. While these systems offer enhanced security features, they are more challenging to implement and require specialized sensors called tablets (Batista et al., 2012).

In recent times, security procedures have gained significant importance due to their reliability and accuracy in achieving desired outcomes. Biometrics, as a modern security procedure, plays a crucial role by isolating and measuring unique biological or behavioral characteristics to authenticate a person's claimed identity. This authentication is accomplished by comparing and matching their distinct biological feature with a known authentic sample (Maiano et al., 2020). The isolation and measurement of biological characteristics hold great significance in contemporary security procedures as they enable the verification of an individual's claimed identity by assessing a specific biological attribute and comparing it to a trusted reference sample.

Furthermore, the identification of individuals can be accomplished by comparing these measurements with a comprehensive database containing information about a known population (Ameral et al., 2019).

Biometrics have become the preferred method of authentication compared to traditional PIN-based approaches for several reasons (Mahalakshimi and Purushothaman, 2017). Biometrics necessitate the physical presence of the person during the verification process, whereas a PIN can be shared or entrusted to others, leading to doubts regarding positive identification (Dimauro et al., 2015; Breebaart et al., 2017). While biometric authentication was previously conducted by human forensic experts, advancements in computing technologies over the past two decades have enabled the automation of this process, making it feasible to deploy biometric authentication systems in commercial environments, in addition to their traditional use in the criminal justice system (Baum et al., 2018).

To enroll a user into the system, specific measurements of their unique biological characteristics are taken. These measurements create a digital representation that is stored in a database, along with supplementary information such as a PIN associated with the individual (Raaghuram, 2020). Whenever the user needs to be identified, such as when accessing a secure area or conducting a financial transaction, the scan is repeated, and the PIN is entered into the verification terminal. An algorithm then compares this code to the one stored in the database to determine the authenticity of the claimed identity (Young et al., 2017; Chakraborty et al., 2019).

The introduction of smartcards revolutionized the storage of codes for personal identification. Users carry the card and present it whenever their identification is required. The code generated during the second scan is compared to the encrypted code on the card, eliminating the need for a central user database (Brand et al., 2019).

The effectiveness of biometric identification schemes is typically evaluated based on three criteria:

- 1) False-acceptance rate (FAR): This measures the percentage of authentication attempts that are falsely accepted as true.
- 2) False-rejection rate (FRR): This measures the percentage of authentication attempts that are falsely rejected as false.
- 3) Processing time: This refers to the time required for authentication processes.

Biometric identification schemes face a trade-off between FAR and FRR, as these rates often oppose each other. To reduce the FRR of a system, the allowable variance must be increased, which naturally leads to a higher FAR (Batista et al., 2012). The optimal performance point for a system is achieved when the FAR and FRR intersect, known as the equal error rate (EER). The goal of biometric authentication schemes is to achieve the lowest possible EER, which often involves the development of complex algorithms to process and compare the measured biological features (Vimal, 2015). The field of biometrics is actively engaged in research efforts to

develop such algorithms. Different biological features can be used for person identification, each with its own advantages and limitations. The choice of identifying features largely depends on the specific context in which they will be utilized (Andrew, 2015).

When selecting a biometric method for a particular application, several factors need to be taken into account. These include:

- a. The required level of reliability.
- b. The costs associated with development and deployment.
- c. The demographics of the target population.
- d. The operating environment in which the system will be used.
- e. The desired speed of operation.
- f. The vulnerability to forgery.

III. REVIEW OF RELEVANT RESEARCH WORKS ON SIGNATURE VERIFICATION

Mahalakshmi and Purushothaman (2017) investigated the application of a finger vein pattern recognition approach within a multi-modal biometric system for human identification. Their research involved utilizing artificial intelligence techniques to create a finger vein recognition system specifically designed for student identification. However, the study encountered challenges in achieving satisfactory verification accuracy due to the presence of noise in the input data.

In a separate study, Yang et al. (2017) introduced a student information management system that employed finger identification and secure data transmission. Their approach incorporated the use of finger images as input and utilized artificial intelligence techniques for identity verification. Although the study demonstrated some level of success during testing, there is still room for improvement in terms of accuracy.

Nawaf (2016) conducted research on a signature recognition system implemented using a Digital Signal Processor (DSP). The primary focus of the study was to develop an automatic signature recognition system by employing holistic feature extraction, specifically utilizing global features extracted from low-frequency data within the signature image. The research showcased the potential of a digital signal processor in aiding signature recognition, achieving a commendable accuracy rate of 95% during testing with a database of 10 AT&T images. However, the recognition performance for RGB images (colored and unfiltered images) was found to be unsatisfactory.

Received: 22 July 2023

Revised: 2 August 2023

Final Accepted: 8 August 2023

Copyright © authors 2023

DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8223420>

Urvashi and Rohit (2019) conducted a survey on methods for signature detection and feature extraction. Their research explored various techniques in these areas. They found that the Template-Based method for signature recognition is straightforward to implement but may face challenges in accurately capturing the global signature structure. The Color Segmentation-Based method's results can be influenced by different color models and variations in illumination. The Appearance-Based method represents optical feature points that can effectively depict the global signature structure. Lastly, the Geometric-Based method offers stability and scale-invariant features. However, the study does not provide conclusive evidence for a method that achieves precise identical signature recognition, as not all methods were reviewed by the authors.

In another study, Andrew (2015) investigated a combination approach for signature recognition systems. The primary objective of their research was to develop a signature recognition system that surpasses existing solutions in terms of accuracy. Their implementation focused on combining the principal component analysis (PCA) and Gabor appearance-based recognition approaches. The study concluded that through this combined approach, a signature recognition system with improved accuracy could be achieved.

Vimal and Virender (2015) examined the implementation and performance analysis of signature recognition using Matlab. Their work introduced a signature recognition system developed to identify an input signature from a set of training signatures. Additionally, they analyzed signature recognition using the edge detection method, which extracts the edges of an image. According to their findings, the edge detector produces a binary image in which white pixels closely approximate the true edges of the original image. They asserted that implementing edge detection techniques can yield more accurate results due to their positive attributes, such as being less sensitive to noise and more adaptive. However, the study lacked comprehensive image processing techniques to further enhance accuracy, speed, and efficiency of the results.

A. Methodology and System Analysis

The Agile Development Methodology:

Agile refers to a flexible approach to software development that involves multiple iterations. It encompasses a set of software development methods based on iterative development, where requirements and solutions evolve through collaboration among self-organizing and cross-functional teams.

Agile is a team-based, iterative approach to development that emphasizes the rapid delivery of a fully functional application in modular components. Instead of creating rigid tasks and schedules, the overall timeline is divided into phases called "sprints," each with a defined duration (usually weeks) and a list of planned deliverables established at the beginning of the sprint.

The term "Agile" was coined in 2001 when the Agile Manifesto was formulated, promoting a time-boxed, iterative approach that enables teams and organizations to respond quickly and accurately to project requirements.

According to Barry Boehm (2011), "Plan-driven" methods are typically most effective when developers can determine system requirements in advance and when these requirements remain relatively stable, with minimal changes occurring monthly.

On the other hand, the agile software development methodology consists of practices that employ iterative and incremental techniques, allowing teams to work together more efficiently and effectively in the development of complex projects.

The Agile Scrum Framework:

The Scrum is a simple way to manage complex projects. It includes roles, events, artifacts, and rules. Amazon and Netflix both use Scrum. The main idea is to break down software development into sprints, allowing for effective progress. Scrum teams work strategically, with key roles like Scrum master and product owner constantly improving daily scrums for productive sprints.

Reasons for Adopting the Agile Methodology in this Study:

After conducting a comprehensive review of various software development models and methodologies, we concluded that the agile software development methodology, specifically following the scrum framework, was the most suitable for this study. Our decision was based on the following reasons:

- a) Extensive statistics indicate that Agile Development Methodology is the most popular choice among software development methodologies for 2021. For instance:
- b) According to Capterra, 71% of companies are currently implementing Agile.
- c) Research by VersionOne reveals that Agile adoption has proven beneficial for 98% of companies.
- d) Harvard Business Review reports that 60% of companies have experienced revenue growth and increased profits after adopting the Agile approach.
- e) The Standish Group Chaos Study states that Agile has a success rate of 42%, compared to the Waterfall model's success rate of 26%. This demonstrates that Agile is 1.5 times more successful than the Waterfall model.
- f) Agile has become the standard and has replaced Waterfall as the preferred model for most software development and management projects.

Considering these factors, we determined that the Agile methodology offered the most advantages and was widely accepted within the industry.

B. Analysis of the developed system

The new system was developed using clustering technique from the unsupervised type of machine learning for student signature verification. In the new system the signature data was collected from the institution and then trained with a clustered machine learning algorithm to generate a reference signature model, which was used for the verification of student identity for class attendance. The problem of noise attributes with the data was addressed using image processing techniques, while quality of feature extraction was also enhanced with geometric extraction approach. The block diagram used for better analysis was presented in figure 1

Figure 1.0: Block diagram of the new system

The figure 1.0 presented the block diagram of the new system which operated by comparing image from the database and also testing images of student signature to verify the person identity. The image upload before verification is processed via filtration using binarization approach which reduces the excess frequencies of the image, then edge detection was used to reveal the patterns of the drawing. This processed data was normalized with resizing approach, before extraction into compact feature vector for training and recognition result.

i. Input to the system

Figure 2.0: Sample of signatures

ii. *Output to the new system*

The major output is the result of the processing input signature. The system compares the query signature and the existing signature in the database for recognition process.

Figure 3.0: flow chart of the signature verification

The figure 3.0 presented the flow chart of the signature verification system which was used for class attendance. The student data was first uploaded as the training set and the process using binarization, normalization and feature extraction approach respectively, before training with clustering to generate the reference signature model which is the intelligence used by the system for signature verification. The flow chart of the system as a signature verification was presented in figure 4.0;

Figure 4.0: flow chart for signature based class attendance verification system

The figure 4.0 presented the flow chart of the class attendance system, showing how testing signature of query student was uploaded by the system and then process for classification using the reference signature model. The verification outcome when matched showed that the student is recognized, but else the student is not recognized.

Figure 5.0: Signature verification result

Figure 6.0: result of the forged and authentic signatures to be verified

Figure 7.0: result of not matched signatures

IV. CONCLUSION

In this work, we have studied different aspects of online signature verification. A digitized tablet with orthogonal sensors used for collecting signature samples. It can collect axial pen tilt and pen pressure in x and y -directions with 64 level with maximum signal report rate 200Hz. We have collected about 1530 authentic signatures for individuals were collected in which 45 were males and 6 were females used for this experiment. From this experiment we noticed that we trained individually trained each feature and as well trained in the group. We developed a authentication system that

- I. Scales easily as new features are added,
- II. Allows to build separate, possibly different HMMs for the different features, and
- III. Optimally combines features to compute the likelihood that a given signatures is genuine from the likelihoods for the individual features.

We used left-right HMMs for modeling the individual dynamic features act as they allow only for marginal deviations from a representative sequence both in sequence values (vertical deviations) and timing information (horizontal information). We then applied the clustering algorithm to efficiently compute the optimal operating points on the receiver operating characteristic curves, i.e., for a given selection of features and a chosen acceptable false alarm rate (i.e., the probability of rejecting a genuine signature), the algorithm computes the optimally achievable probability of detecting a fraudulent signature. This gives the user control over the system performance in a rigorous fashion.

Received: 22 July 2023

Revised: 2 August 2023

Final Accepted 8 August 2023

Copyright © authors 2023

DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8223420>

REFERENCE

- [1]. Ahmed, M.L. Baena, D. Elizondo, E.L. Rubio, E.J. Palomo and T. Watson, Assessment of geometric features for individual identification and verification in signature hand systems Expert Systems with Applications 40(9) (2013) 3580-3594.
- [2]. Ameral, T. Bailador, C. Avila, J. Guerra-Casanova and A. Santos, Sierra Analysis of pattern recognition techniques for in-air signature signatures, Pattern Recognition 44(10-11) (2011) 2468-2478.
- [3]. Asogwa T.O. Digital face recognition system for digital crime detection. September 2018. 44(10-11) (2018) 2555-2564.
- [4]. Batista, E. Granger and R. Sabourin, Dynamic selection of generative discriminative ensembles for off-line signature verification, Pattern Recognition 45(4) (2012) 1326-1340.
- [5]. Baum and G. Sell, Growth functions for transformations on manifolds, Pasive Journal of Mathematics 27(2) (1968) 211-227.
- [6]. Baum and T. Petrie, (2012) "Statistical inference for probabilistic functions of finite"; Recognition Letters 33(8) (2012) 965-969.
- [7]. Baum, An inequality and associated maximization technique in statistical estimation for probabilistic functions of markov processes, Inequalities 3 (1972) 1-Baum and J. Egon, An inequality with applications to statistical estimation for probabilistic functions of a Markov process and to a model for ecology, Bulletin of Amererican Mathematical Society 73(3) (1967) 360-363.
- [8]. Baum, T. Petrie, G. Soules and N. Weiss, A maximization technique occurring in the statistical analysis of probabilistic functions of Markov chains, Annals of Mathematical Statistics 41(1) (1970) 164-171.
- [9]. Bengio and P. Frasconi, Input output hmms for sequence processing, IEEE
- [10]. Bourlard and N. Morgan, Hybrid HMM/ANN Systems for Speech Recognition, Overview and New Research Directions Springer- Verlag 1997.
- [11]. Brand, N. Oliver and A. Pentland, (2014) "Coupled hidden Markov models for complexaction recognition, MIT Media Lab Perceptual Computing Learning and
- [12]. Brault and R. Plamondon, (2014) A complexity measure of handwritten curves: Modelling of dynamic signature forgery, IEEE Transactions on Systems, Man and
- [13]. Brault and R. Plamondon (2016) "How to detect problematic signers for automatic; Recognition Letters 33(4) pp. 965-969.
- [14]. Breebaart, I. Buhan, K. Groot and E. Kelkboom (2017), Evaluation of a template protection approach to integrate fingerprint signatures in a PIN-based payment infrastructure, Electronic Commerce Research and Application pp. 605-614.
- [15]. Bridle, A. (2019): A recurrent 'neural' network architecture with a idden Markov model interpretation, Speech Communication 9(1) 8392.

Received: 22 July 2023

Revised: 2 August 2023

Final Accepted 8 August 2023

Copyright © authors 2023

DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8223420>

- [16]. Broek, Beyond signatures, *Procedia Computer Science* 1(1) (2010) 2511- 2519.
- [17]. Bromley, J. Bentz, L. Bottou, I.G.Y. Lecun, C. Moore, E. Sackinger and R.
- [18]. Castaldi and E.S. Gomez, A new spontaneous pupillary oscillation-based verification system, *Expert Systems with Applications* 40(13) (2013) 5352-5362.
- [19]. Chakraborty, V. Balasubramanian and S. Panchanathan, Generalized batch mode active learning for signature-based signature recognition, *Pattern Recognition* 46(2) (2013) 497-508.
- [20]. Chuang and M.C. Chen, An anonymous multi-server authenticated key agreement scheme based on trust computing using smart cards and signatures *Expert Systems with Applications* 41(4) (2014) 1411-1418.
- [21]. Cummings, M.S. Nixon and J.N. Carter, The image ray transform for structural feature detection, *Pattern Recognition Letters* 32(15) (2011) 2053-2060.
- [22]. Dimauro, S. Impedovo and G. Pirlo, Component-oriented algorithms for signature verification, *International Journal of Pattern Recognition and Artificial intelligence*; vol 4; issue 1; 2018.
- [23]. H. Crane and J. Ostrem, Automatic signature verification using a three-axis force sensitive pen, *IEEE Transactions on Systems, Man and Cybernetics* 13(3) (1994) 749-770. verification, in proceedings of the NBS Trends and Applications 32 1977.
- [24]. Mariano, L.M. Amaral, A.J. Lopes, J.M. Jansen, A.C.D. Faria and P.L. Melo, An improved method of early diagnosis of smoking-induced respiratory changes using machine learning algorithms, *Computer Methods and Programs in Biomedicine* 112(3) (2014) 441-454.
- [26]. Raaghuram Sringt. Signature verification using a siamese time delay neural network, *International Journal of Pattern Recognition and Artificial Intelligence* 7(4) (2014) 669-688.